

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

I. ASYMPTOTIC FORMULAS FOR THE SOLUTIONS OF LINEAR INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION $l(y) = \lambda y$

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ABSTRACT

In the paper we consider in $L^2(R^+)$, where R^+ is a semi-axis $(0, \infty)$, a second order integro-differential equation

$$y''(x) + \lambda y(x) = p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^{\infty} k(x, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds \quad (0.1)$$

and a boundary condition

$$y'(0) - \theta y(0) = 0 \quad (0.2)$$

where θ is a fixed complex number, while $\sqrt{\lambda} = \rho$, $Im\rho > 0$.

$\rho(x)$ is a complex valued summable function in the interval R^+ and the kernel of the integro-differential equation (0.1) has the form

$$K(x, s, \rho) = \begin{cases} e^{-\rho\omega_1(s-x)}\rho(s)k^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s < x, \\ e^{-\rho\omega_2(s-x)}\rho(s)k^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s > x, \end{cases} \quad (0.3)$$

where ω_1, ω_2 are different roots of second degree from -1, while $k^*(x, s, \rho)$ is a complex (x, s, ρ) , valued continuous bounded function in totality of variables $0 \leq x, s < \infty$, $Im\rho > 0$ and analytic with respect to ρ in the domain $Im\rho > 0$ for each fixed (x, s) , $0 \leq x, s < \infty$.

If the condition

$$\int_a^{\infty} |\rho(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^{\infty} |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B < \infty \quad (0.4)$$

and $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $Im\rho > 0$, where $r > B$ is fulfilled, then the integro-differential equation (0.1) has a solution $y_1(x, \rho)$ analytic with respect to ρ in the domain for each fixed $x \in (0, \infty)$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(1)}{\rho\omega_1} \right], \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty,$$

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} [\rho\omega_1 + 0(1)], \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

Keywords: integro-differential equation, asymptotics, conditions, variable, complex valued, bounded function, in the domain, solution, semi-axis, uniformly, proof, lemma.

Introduction.

We denote by L_{θ} an operator generated by the integro-differential expression

$$l(y) \equiv -y''(x) + p(x)y(x) + \int_0^{\infty} k(x, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds$$

and boundary condition (0.2) in Hilbert space $L_2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. The domain of definition $D(L_\theta)$ of the integro-differential operator L_θ consists of the functions $y(x)$ with a derivative $y'(x)$, absolutely continuous in each finite interval $(\alpha, \beta) \subset \mathbb{R}^+$, satisfying the boundary condition (0.2) and such that $y(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $l(y) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. If $y(x) \in D(L_\theta)$, then by the definition $L_\theta y = l(y)$. We now consider in $L_2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ the integro-differential equation

$$l(y) = \lambda y \quad (1.1)$$

we rewrite it in the form

$$y''(x) + \lambda y(x) = p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^\infty k(x, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds. \quad (1.2)$$

Assume $\sqrt{\lambda} = \rho = \rho_1 + \omega_1 \rho_2$, $\text{Im} \rho > 0$. Asymptotic behavior of the solutions to equation (1.2) depend on what part of the complex plane the point in ρ is located.

Applying to the integro-differential equation (1.2) the method of variation of arbitrary constant, we obtain the integro-differential equation

$$y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i e^{\rho \omega_i x} + \frac{\omega_1}{2\rho} \int_x^\infty [e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)}] \times \\ \times \left[\rho(\tau)y'(\tau, \rho) + \int_0^\infty k(\tau, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds \right] d\tau. \quad (1.3)$$

Considering condition (0.3) we obtain

$$y(x, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^2 c_i e^{\rho \omega_i x} + \frac{\omega_1}{2\rho} \int_x^\infty \rho(\tau) \{ e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} + \\ + \int_x^\infty [e^{\rho \omega_1(x-2s+\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)}] k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \} y'(\tau, \rho) d\tau. \quad (1.4)$$

Theorem 1.1. Let the condition (0.4) be fulfilled, and $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $\text{Im} \rho > 0$, where $r > B$. Then for $c_1 = 1, c_2 = 0$, the equation (1.4) has the solution $y_1(x, \rho)$ analytic with respect to ρ in this domain for each fixed $x \in [a, \infty]$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(1)}{\rho \omega_1} \right], \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty, \quad (1.5a)$$

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} [\rho \omega_1 + 0(1)], \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty. \quad (1.5b)$$

(1.5b) follows form $y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(1)}{\rho \omega_1} \right]$, as $x \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. Put to the equation (1.4) $c_1 = 1, c_2 = 0$ and arrive at the equation

$$y(x, \rho) = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} + \frac{\omega_1}{2\rho} \int_x^\infty \rho(\tau) \{ e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} + \\ + \int_x^\infty [e^{\rho \omega_1(x-2s+\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)}] k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \} y'(\tau, \rho) d\tau. \quad (1.6)$$

Differentiating formally with respect to x both parts of identities (1.6) once, we obtain

$$y'(x, \rho) = \rho \omega_1 e^{\rho \omega_1 x} + \frac{\omega_1}{2\rho} \int_x^\infty \rho p(\tau) \{ \omega_1 e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} - \omega_2 e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left[\int_0^\infty \rho \omega_1 e^{\rho \omega_1(x-2s+\tau)} - \rho \omega_2 e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} \right] k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \Big\} y'(\tau, s) d\tau = \\
 & = \rho \omega_1 e^{\rho \omega_1 x} - \frac{1}{2} \int_x^\infty \rho(\tau) e^{\rho \omega_1(x-\tau)} - e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} \int_0^\infty \left\{ e^{\rho \omega_1(x-2s+\tau)} - \rho \omega_2 e^{\rho \omega_2(x-\tau)} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \cdot k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} y'(\tau, s) d\tau.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.7}$$

Put in (1.7)

$$y'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho \omega_1 x} \cdot z(x, \rho). \tag{1.8}$$

Then for the functions $z(x, \rho)$ we obtain the integral equations

$$z(x, \rho) = \rho \omega_1 + Hz, \tag{1.9}$$

where

$$Hz = - \int_0^\infty \rho(\tau) \left\{ \frac{1 - e^{2\rho \omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2} - \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{2\rho \omega_1(\tau-s)} - e^{2\rho \omega_2(\tau-x)}}{2} k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} z(\tau, \rho) d\tau.$$

We carry out proof for the equation (1.9).

We write the solution of the equation (1.9) in the form of the Neumann series

$$z(x, \rho) = \rho \omega_1 + H1 + H^2 1 + \dots \tag{1.10}$$

We show that the series (1.10) uniformly converges for all ρ in the domain $Jm\rho > 0$.

In fact, for $\tau > x \geq a$, $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $Jm\rho > 0$ we have

$$\frac{1 + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} \leq \frac{1}{r}, \frac{e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-s)} + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} \leq \frac{1}{r}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 |H1| & \leq \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ \frac{1 + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} + \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-s)} + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} d\tau \leq \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \frac{B}{r}; \\
 |H^2 1| & \leq \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ \frac{1 + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} + \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-s)} + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} |H1| d\tau \leq \\
 & \leq \frac{B}{r^2} \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \frac{B^2}{r^2};
 \end{aligned}$$

by induction

$$|H^n 1| \leq \frac{B^n}{r^n}.$$

If $B < r$, the series $\rho \omega_1 + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{B^n}{r^n}$ converges. Therefore, the series (1.10) for $x \geq a$ is majorized by

the convergent number series $\rho \omega_1 + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{B^n}{r^n}$ and this means that its sum $z(x, \rho)$ will be analytic with respect

to ρ in the domain $|\rho| \geq r > 0, Jm\rho > 0$ for each fixed $x \in [a, +\infty]$.

Since the sum $z(x, \rho)$ of the series (1.10) by modulus does not exceed the sum of the series $\rho\omega_1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{B^n}{r^n}$, this implies the boundedness of $z(x, \rho)$ in the domain $x \in [a, \infty]$, $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $Jm\rho > 0$.

Let $|z(x, \rho)| \leq A$.

Let us estimate the integral term in (1.9)

$$|Hz| \leq A|H1| \leq \frac{A}{r} \int_x^{\infty} |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ 1 + \int_0^{\infty} |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \rightarrow 0[1], \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence, $z(x, \rho) = \rho\omega_1 + 0(1)$ uniformly with respect to ρ in the domain $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $Jm\rho > 0$.

Considering this result in $y'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} z(x, \rho)$, we obtain (1.5b). Hence it follows that

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(1)}{\rho\omega_1} \right], \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

Obviously, the function $y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(1)}{\rho\omega_1} \right]$ will satisfy the equation (1.4) for

$c_1 = 1; c_2 = 0$. It is easy to verify directly that it will be a solution of the integro-differential equation (1.11) as well. It is clear that

$$\begin{aligned} y'(x, \rho) &= \rho\omega_1 e^{\rho\omega_1 x} - \frac{1}{2} \int_x^{\infty} \rho(\tau) \left\{ e^{\rho\omega_1 x} + e^{\rho\omega_1(2\tau-x)} + \right. \\ &\left. + \int_0^{\infty} \left[e^{\rho\omega_1(x+2\tau-2s)} + e^{\rho\omega_1(2\tau-x)} \right] k^*(s, \tau, \rho) ds \right\} z(\tau, \rho) d\tau. \end{aligned} \quad (1.11)$$

By the boundedness of the functions $z(x, \rho)$ the last integral converges uniformly and therefore the differentiation under the integral sign is legal.

The solution $y_1(x, \rho)$ can be obviously, continued also on the interval $(0, a)$, constructing in this interval the solution of the integro-differential equation (1.1) satisfying the conditions

$$y^{(k)}(a, \rho) = y_1^{(k)}(a), \quad k = 0, 1.$$

Then $y_1(x, \rho)$ will be an analytic function of ρ in the same domain for $0 \leq x \leq a$ as well.

Theorem 1.1 is proved.

Behaving in the same way we can prove the following statement.

Theorem 1.2. Let (0.4) be fulfilled, and $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $Jm\rho > 0$, where $r > B$. Then $c_1 = 0, c_2 = 1$ for the equation (1.4) has the solution $y_2(x, \rho)$ analytic with respect to ρ in this domain for each fixed $x \in (0, \infty)$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$\begin{aligned} y_2(x, \rho) &= e^{\rho\omega_2 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(1)}{\rho\omega_2} \right], \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty \\ y_2'(x, \rho) &= e^{\rho\omega_2 x} [\rho\omega_2 + 0(1)], \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1.1. For $Jm\rho > 0$, $\rho \rightarrow \infty$

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + 0\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right]$$

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[\rho\omega_1 + 0\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right]$$

uniformly with respect to x from the interval R^+ .

Proof. We again consider the equation (1.9). For rather large r we can assume $a = 0$.

Let $|z(x, \rho)| \leq A$. Then

$$|Hz| \leq A|H1| \leq \frac{A}{|\rho|} \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \frac{AB}{|\rho|} \rightarrow 0\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right), \text{ as } \rho \rightarrow \infty.$$

Then $z(x, \rho) = 1 + 0\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right)$.

Substituting in $y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} z(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + 0\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right]$.

In a similar way, it follows from (1.7) that

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[\rho\omega_1 + 0\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right].$$

Now, let the following condition be fulfilled:

$$|\rho(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right] \leq ce^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}, \quad \varepsilon_0 > 0 \tag{1.12}$$

Then

$$\int_0^\infty e^{2\varepsilon x} |\rho(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B_1 < \infty, \tag{1.13}$$

where $\varepsilon_0 > \varepsilon > 0$ and B_1 is independent of ρ .

Theorem 1.3. Let the condition (1.12) be fulfilled and $Im\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$. Then for $c_1 = 1, c_2 = 0$ equation

(1.7) has the solution $y_1(x, \rho)$ analytic with respect to ρ in this domain for each fixed $x \in R^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[1 + \frac{0(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x})}{\rho\omega_1} \right] \text{ as } x \rightarrow +\infty, \tag{1.14}$$

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} \left[\rho\omega_1 + 0(e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}) \right] \text{ as } x \rightarrow +\infty. \tag{1.15}$$

Proof. Put in the equation (1.4) $c_1 = 1, c_2 = 0, y_1'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} z(x, \rho)$, then we arrive at the equation (1.9).

We write its solution in the form of the Neumann series

$$z(x, \rho) = \rho\omega_1 + H1 + H^2 1 + \dots \tag{1.16}$$

Show that the series (1.16) converges uniformly for all ρ in the domain $Im\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$.

In fact for $\tau > x, Im\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$, we have

$$e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)} < e^{\varepsilon_0(\tau-x)}.$$

Since then

$$\begin{aligned}
|H1| &\leq \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ \frac{1 + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} + \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-s)} + e^{-2\rho_2(\tau-x)}}{2} |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \\
&\leq \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| e^{\varepsilon_0(\tau-x)} \left\{ \frac{e^{-\varepsilon_0(\tau-x)} + 1}{2} + \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-\varepsilon_0(s-x)} + 1}{2} |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \\
&\leq \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| e^{\varepsilon_0(\tau-x)} \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau.
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\tau > x \geq 0$, then $\varepsilon - x = t \geq 0$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
|H1| &\leq \int_0^\infty |\rho(x+t)| e^{\varepsilon_0 t} \left\{ 1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(s, x+\tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \\
&\leq c \int_0^\infty e^{-2\varepsilon_0(x+t)} \cdot e^{\varepsilon_0 t} dt = \frac{cc_1}{\varepsilon_0} e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x},
\end{aligned}$$

where $c_1 = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_0}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
|H^2 1| &\leq \int_x^\infty |\rho(\tau)| \left\{ \frac{1 - e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\omega_1} + \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-s)} - e^{2\rho\omega_1(\tau-x)}}{2\omega_1} |k^*(s, \tau, \rho)| ds \right\} d\tau \leq \\
&\leq \frac{(cc_1)^2}{\varepsilon_0} \int_0^\infty e^{-2\varepsilon_0(x+t)} \cdot e^{\varepsilon_0 t} \cdot e^{-2\varepsilon_0(x+t)} dt = \frac{(cc_1)^2 \cdot e^{-4\varepsilon_0 x}}{1 \cdot 3 \varepsilon_0^2};
\end{aligned}$$

by the induction

$$|H^n 1| \leq \frac{(cc_1)^n}{(2n-1)!! \varepsilon_0^n} e^{-2n\varepsilon_0 x}$$

where $(2n-1)!! = 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdots (2n-1)$.

Since the series (1.16) for each fixed $x \in R^+$ is majorized by the convergent number series, this means that its sum $z(x, \rho)$ will be analytic with respect to (ρ) in the domain $Jm\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$ for each fixed $x \in R^+$.

Since the sum $z(x, \rho)$ of the series (1.16) by the modulus, does not exceed the sum of the series

$$1 + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{(cc_1)^n}{(2n-1)!! \varepsilon_0^n} e^{-2n\varepsilon_0 x}$$

hence it follows the boundedness $z(x, \rho)$ in $0 \leq x < \infty$, $Jm\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$. $|z(x, \rho)| \leq A_1$.

Obviously, the function

$$y_1'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1 x} z(x, \rho)$$

will satisfy for $c_1 = 1$, $c_2 = 0$ the equation (1.4) and it can be easily verified that it also will be a solution of the integro-differential equation (1.1).

We now estimate the integral term in (1.16)

$$|H1| \leq A_1 |H1| \leq \frac{A_1 cc_1}{\varepsilon_0} e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x} \rightarrow 0 (e^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}) \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

Therefore, $z(x, \rho) = \rho\omega_1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x})$ uniformly with respect to ρ in the domain $0 \leq x < \infty$, $\text{Im}\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}$. Put in $y_1'(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1x} z(x, \rho)$. Then we obtain (1.15).

Now

$$\frac{dy_1(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_1x} [\rho\omega_1 + o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x})]$$

hence we obtain

$$y_1(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_1x} \left[1 + \frac{o(e^{-2\varepsilon_0x})}{\rho\omega_1} \right] \text{ as } x \rightarrow +\infty.$$

We can easily prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1.5. Let the condition (0.4) be fulfilled and $|\rho| \geq r > 0$, $\text{Im}\rho > 0$, where $r > B$. Then the integro-differential equation (1.1) in the half-plane $\text{Im}\rho > 0$, has two linearly independent solutions $y_k(x, \rho)$, $k=1,2$ analytic in his domain with respect to ρ for each fixed $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and admitting the asymptotics

$$y_k(x, \rho) = e^{\rho\omega_kx} \left[1 + \frac{o(1)}{\rho\omega_k} \right] \text{ as } x \rightarrow +\infty,$$

$$\frac{dy_k(x, \rho)}{dx} = e^{\rho\omega_kx} [\rho\omega_k + o(1)] \text{ as } x \rightarrow \infty, k=1,2.$$

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